

EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT TOWARDS ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE OF COMPANY M

Ma. Melissa D. Paguirigan, MBA
Dr. Heidi R. Maneclang

*Master in Business Administration Program
Colegio de San Juan de Letran Calamba – Laguna, Philippines*

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ABSTRACT

The level of employee engagement in work is an essential predictor of work performance. Sustaining it to a greater extent would help Company M to improve its organizational performance. This study determined 1) the level of organizational performance in terms of financial and non-financial dimensions; 2) the level of employee engagement according to leadership, communication, career opportunities, nature of job and compensation and benefits of Company M's business support functions; 3) the model that significantly impacted the organizational performance of Company M; and 4) the strategies formulated and to be implemented by Company M to increase employee engagement towards organizational performance. A mixed methods approach applying the sequential explanatory research design was used to support the objectives of the study. The data were gathered in quantitative and qualitative phases with 150 respondents and three participants from each employee level. The quantitative data were analyzed through frequencies, percentages, means, and stepwise regression while qualitative data were presented through summaries of thematic constructs and analysis. The findings of the study revealed that Company M's level of organizational performance in terms of overall financial and non-financial dimensions exhibited "neither good nor poor relative performance" and "good relative performance", respectively. Its level of employee engagement indicated that "employees were engaged" by almost all the engagement drivers except for compensation and benefits where "employees were neither engaged nor disengaged". Most of the models formulated revealed that "leadership" was the most significant and strongest predictor while "nature of job" was the least significant predictor. Few significant employee engagement variables affected organizational performance variables inversely due to certain factors as validated through the qualitative interviews. The researcher recommended that the formulated strategies be adopted by Company M;

a similar study be conducted by other companies to cover all employees and other employee engagement variables for more extensive findings.

Keywords: *Career Opportunities, Communication, Compensation and Benefits, Employee Engagement, Engagement Drivers, Leadership, Nature of Job, Organizational Performance*

INTRODUCTION

The local and global economies are becoming very dynamic. Industries worldwide are becoming more competitive to adapt to the fast-developing changes brought about by technology and several other factors. To cope with these inevitable changes, organizations must develop strategic plans to survive and remain in the loop of conducting their businesses. It is for this reason that organizations need people who are committed to the challenges of making things happen by making the right decisions at the right time. Employees who are engaged produce results more and fulfill customer's requirements better. Keeping them engaged in their jobs is an unceasing challenge. Company M has a workforce of more than 900 employees who contributed to the success of its business despite the pandemic. Investing on their engagement will drive the business back to its normal pace. Through the measurement and identification of the engagement drivers, the company can determine the extent of its impact and can install strategies to increase employee engagement and organizational performance.

Research Objectives

This study provided a clear insight into the impact of employee engagement on the organizational performance of Company M. The following were the specific objectives for the analysis in this study:

1. To measure the level of organizational performance of Company M in terms of: a) Financial dimensions and b) Non-Financial dimensions;
2. To determine the level of employee engagement of Company M according to the following drivers: a) Leadership, b) Communication, c) Career Opportunities, d) Nature of Job and e) Compensation and Benefits.
3. To formulate a model containing engagement drivers that significantly impact the organizational performance of Company M; and
4. To create strategies to be implemented by Company M to increase employee engagement towards organizational performance.

Research Framework

The theoretical framework that the researcher used as basis for the study was the Social Exchange Theory (SET) which originated from an American sociologist, George Homans, in 1958 when he published an article named "Social Behavior as Exchange"

(Tulane University, 2018). The SET theoretical basis substantiates the reasons why employees choose to engage in their work, either in a good or bad way, depending on the economic and socio-emotional resources gained from their institution, or even choose to remain in their institution (Dajani, 2015).

The study was guided by the flowchart shown in Figure 1 illustrating the measurement and analysis of the organizational performance and employee engagement of Company M. Then, a model was developed to depict the significant engagement drivers affecting the organizational performance of Company M and was used as basis to formulate specific strategies for enhancing employee engagement and organizational performance.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework of the study

Significance of the Study

Theory. This research tested the applicability of the Social Exchange Theory (SET) which explains why employees opt to remain in their work, according to the economic and socio-emotional benefits derived from the organization (Dajani, 2015). This study will guide other manufacturing industries in assessing their organizational performance and engagement.

Policy. This research will be useful to the management of Company M in creating and implementing policies and strategies that will increase organizational performance by identifying and improving the extent of employee engagement.

Practice. The knowledge that will be obtained from this research may help 1) the officers of Company M and other business leaders in evaluating the level of employee engagement in improving business' performance; 2) the employees in achieving job satisfaction and engagement and producing quality work; and 3) the researcher in applying the knowledge and skills in enhancing employee engagement towards organizational performance.

Social Action. This research may contribute to society by assisting business leaders and employees in other industries to set and sustain suitable policies and programs so that organizational performance will be achieved through employee engagement.

Scope and Limitations

The study was only limited to the perceptions of employees under business support functions of Company M at the time the survey was done as well as in the determination of the significant engagement contributors to organizational performance of Company M and establishment of strategies to enhance engagement.

Definition of Terms

Career opportunities. The professional development of employees.

Communication. The act of transferring information from one place, person or group to another. It involves one sender, a message and a recipient.

Compensation. The salaries received by the employee from an employer.

Employee or personal engagement. This refers to "the harnessing of organization members' selves to their work roles; in engagement, people employ and express themselves physically, cognitively, and emotionally during role performances" (Diogene, 2017).

Engagement drivers. The deep-down feelings and emotions that employees have about their position, management and organization which translates to employee needs, well-being and increased levels of energy, passion and action.

Leadership. The leaders or actions of leading in an organization.

Nature of job. The type of work that an employee does.

Organizational performance. The ability of organizations to meet the needs of stakeholders and its own needs for survival (Obeidat, 2016).

Review of Related Literature

Previous research on the topics of employee engagement, its drivers and organizational performance were objectively evaluated to give theoretical basis and to help the researcher determine the type of research to be adopted. The concept of employee engagement was developed by William A. Kahn in 1990 through his study involving summer camp and architecture employees to understand the psychological conditions- meaningfulness, safety and availability that lead to employee's engagement in the workplace (Diogene, 2017). In today's business world, it is vital to understand the specific drivers of employee engagement. Employee engagement was proven to contribute to the businesses' productivity and work performance. The most dominant

factor of employee engagement was leadership aside from work-life balance, communication, and pay and benefits (Othman, Rapi, Alias, Jahya, and Loon, 2019). Vilorio (2018) revealed in his study that the significance of the job as perceived by the employee was the only internal engagement driver. Hoque, Awang, Siddiqui and Sabiu (2018) investigated the positive impact of compensation system on employee performance resulting to employee engagement. The study of Iddagoda and Gunawardana (2017) investigated the connection between employee engagement and perceived financial performance (i.e. profit growth, sales growth, and operating cost) of listed companies where the results showed that employee engagement had significant positive effect on perceived financial performance. A related study by Muller et al. (2018) concluded that employee engagement had a significantly positive impact on organizational performance when the latter was measured using the elements of balanced scorecard.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A mixed methods approach applying the sequential explanatory research design were used to support the set objectives of this study.

Research Locale

The study was performed in Company M, a Japanese manufacturing company engaged in the assembly and distribution of quality trucks, buses, and spare parts.

Population and Sampling Design

The identified population frame of the study was the list of Company M employees under the business support functions as of September 31, 2020 employing the Proportionate Stratified Sampling method with employee category as stratification variable. The sample was determined through the formula of the Philippine Social Science Council Survey.

Research Instrument

The researcher used a survey questionnaire of 35 items employing a 5-point Likert scale through Google forms. The said instrument was a combination of self-constructed statements from the literature review and valid items adapted from previous studies.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher secured permission from Company M to perform the research. Quantitative data were initially collected through the online questionnaire which was validated and tested using Cronbach's coefficient alpha before tabulation and analysis.

The qualitative phase consisted of interviews with three selected participants. The integrated quantitative and qualitative results answered the set objectives of the study.

Management and Treatment of Data

The data analysis developed for this research were as follows:

Table 1. Data Analysis Matrix

RESEARCH QUESTIONS	DATA	INSTRUMENT	ANALYSIS
1. What is the level of organizational performance of Company M in terms of: a) Financial and b) Non-Financial dimensions?	Quantitative → Qualitative	Survey → Questionnaire Interview	Descriptive Thematic Analysis
2. What is the level of employee engagement of Company M according to the following drivers? a) Leadership, b) Communication, c) Career Opportunities, d) Nature of Job, e) Compensation and Benefits	Quantitative → Qualitative	Survey → Questionnaire Interview	Descriptive Thematic Analysis
3. What model can be formulated containing engagement drivers that significantly impact the organizational performance of Company M?	Quantitative → Qualitative	Survey → Questionnaire Interview	Stepwise multiple regression Thematic Analysis
4. What are the strategies to be formulated and implemented by Company M to increase employee engagement towards organizational performance?	Results of the Study	Survey → Questionnaire Interview, Desk Research	Textual Analysis

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The quantitative and qualitative results are presented based on the data analysis discussed in the preceding section. The questionnaire's validity was checked while its reliability was measured using the Cronbach's coefficient alpha test of internal consistency where results showed that all Cronbach's alpha figures calculated were above the threshold- Organizational Performance: Financial Dimension (0.7734) and Non-Financial Dimension (0.8944); Employee Engagement: Leadership (0.8375), Communication (0.8679), Career Opportunities (0.9468), Nature of Job (0.7759), and Compensation and Benefits (0.9535).

I. Level of Organizational Performance

In Table 2, the resulting level of financial organizational performance (with total mean of 3.39) as perceived by the respondents was "neither good nor poor relative performance" which proved that on the average, high profit, positive sales growth and low operating cost of Company M cannot be assured at this time which might be due to the unfavorable financial situation caused by the instability of the economy in the pandemic. Emplify (2019) cited research conducted by Willis Towers Watson which reported that organizations with high employee engagement had up to three times higher operating margin than those with low employee engagement. This result will lead one to infer that Company M might have lower employee engagement because of the respondent's neutral perceptions on its organizational performance. The results also showed that the total mean of 3.65 for the total non-financial dimension translated that the company had a "Good relative performance" which also conformed to the highest percentage of

responses. These results substantiated the study of Muller et. al (2018) that employee engagement had significant influence on the organizational performance. Thus, it can be inferred that the employee engagement of Company M contributed to the good relative performance.

Table 2. Mean ratings and percentage of responses per rating on the level of organizational performance of Company M

DESCRIPTION	MEAN	VERBAL INTERPRETATION	PERCENTAGE OF RESPONSES PER RATING				
			1 - SD	2 - D	3 - N	4 - A	5 - SA
Total Financial Dimension	3.39	Neither good nor poor relative performance	1.57%	9.10%	44.00%	39.07%	6.27%
Total Non-Financial Dimension	3.65	Good relative performance	1.13%	6.00%	28.43%	55.30%	9.13%

Based on the interview with the participants, common themes that emerged for the financial and non-financial organizational performance are illustrated in Table 3.

Table 3. Thematic Analysis and Narratives for Research Question 1

DIMENSION	THEMES	NARRATIVES
Financial	Achieving Profit	<i>I believe that due to the pandemic we have, the sales went low but still we are striving because unlike any other companies, we are still open and operating. There is work meaning there are orders. Profit is not that high.</i>
	Outcomes of sales	<i>The sales team is made aware of the company direction and projection. Employee can align the strategy towards the direction/projection.</i>
	Effect of operating cost	<i>Instead of buying machinery our company is continuing to provide jobs to skilled workers especially on the production line. With that said, there is an operating cost that may be higher than other companies that rely on machineries.</i>
Non-Financial	Managing Customers	<i>This company is in its current state because its customers are treated like kings by having total customer support.</i>
	Managing Internal Processes	<i>The employee's productivity and product/service quality are ensured by monitoring performance of employees and compliance with ISO standards.</i>
	Continuous Quality Improvement	<i>We do not end with just selling our products, we offer after-sales services to our client to provide them quality services even after buying our products.</i>

II. Level of Employee Engagement

In Table 4, the mean ratings of the four engagement drivers indicated that “employees were engaged” and these results were aligned with the highest percentage of responses. These findings were consistent with the studies of Dajani (2015), Obeidat

(2016) and Viloría (2018) that revealed the leadership’s predictive power of employee engagement, the reciprocal interconnection between management and employees and the need to stimulate jobs to support engagement, and that career growth opportunities were vital drivers of productivity and retention. Moreover, the “employees were neither engaged nor disengaged” by compensation and benefits since their perceptions were neutral on three out of its five indicators. With this result, one thing was definite that it is not enough to engage the employees. Company M can be guided by the study of Hoque et. al (2018) that indicated that compensation systems can alleviate employee’s work performance towards engagement.

Table 3. Means and percentage responses on the level of employee engagement

DESCRIPTION	MEAN	VERBAL INTERPRETATION	PERCENTAGE OF RESPONSES PER RATING				
			1 – SD	2 – D	3 – N	4 – A	5-SA
Total Leadership	3.61	Employees were engaged.	2.00%	8.68%	29.18%	46.94%	13.20%
Total Communication	3.70	Employees were engaged.	1.33%	7.20%	28.33%	46.48%	16.68%
Total Career Opportunities	3.62	Employees were engaged.	3.00%	7.15%	30.00%	42.33%	17.53%
Total Nature of Job	3.91	Employees were engaged.	2.50%	2.35%	23.00%	47.65%	24.50%
Total Compensation and Benefits	3.39	Employees were neither engaged nor disengaged.	3.68%	9.68%	36.00%	39.15%	11.50%

The results of the interview with the participants led to emerging themes that showed why and how Company M ensured employee engagement in terms of the five engagement drivers. Table 5 shows the narratives for the themes derived.

Table 4. Thematic analysis and narratives for research question 2

THEMES	NARRATIVES
Leadership Outcomes	<i>To maintain employee engagement, the company must stay as a going concern company through succession planning, and training.</i>
Advantages of Communication	<i>This company maintains communication within the department and company-wide. This is done through information dissemination in the form of email/text blasts, campaign drives and online meetings.</i>
Motivating career advancement programs	<i>Career Opportunities provide challenges, and these vary in every line of work. Not all nature of work in our company has a high career ladder. Having programs for skills development encourage employees to advance their skills.</i>
Engaging Manner of Job Assignment	<i>For better performance of employees, employee’s job should be clear through the orientation upon employment and regular feedback and suggestion from superiors.</i>
Advantages of Compensation and Benefits	<i>This serves as one of the motivating factors that keep me engaged in my work in exchange for my services in the company through the company’s on-time and accurate delivery of fair pay and benefits to employees.</i>

III. Model formulated containing engagement drivers that significantly impact the organizational performance of Company M per combination of variables

The researcher analyzed the data gathered through the Stepwise Regression Method in SPSS which generated the list of key employee engagement predictors of the organizational performance of Company M. The regression determined the characteristics that had the greatest influence on the organizational performance. A final model is identified per scenario or combination of employee engagement and organizational performance variables (i.e. 18 combinations) to come up with detailed analysis and recommended strategies.

Figure 2 shows the resulting significant predictors where leadership consistently showed its strongest impact to total organizational performance, total financial (positive sales growth and lower operating cost) and non-financial dimensions (customer, internal process, learning and innovations performance). However, negative b-coefficient results for career opportunities, compensation and benefits, communication and nature of job variables caused decreasing impact to organizational performance variables. This information provided the researcher to devise strategies to help in turning the negative to positive impact of these engagement predictors to the identified organizational performance variables.

Figure 2. Significant predictors of organizational performance of Company M with unstandardized b coefficients

Common themes per model were derived through interviews as shown in Table 6.

Table 5. Thematic analysis and narratives for research question 3 (Models 1-18)

MODELS	THEMES	NARRATIVES
1	Engaging factors of total organizational performance	The company has existing programs that address the different employee engagement factors (example: training, compensation and benefits, company, kaizen activities) to improve overall organizational performance. These are done through the unified efforts of management and employees.
2	Positive Drivers of Overall Leadership	Leadership style affects company performance through the treatment of employees as partners. Harmonious relationship with employees may lead to company's success.
3 & 4	Drivers of Total Leadership	Many managers are involved in the decision making especially before funding or planning an activity or project, leading to many ideas before execution of plans. Routine meetings and conference to better understand the problem before releasing funds or jumping into the plan.
	Leader's capability	The leaders of Company M are capable to lead and contribute to the financial organizational performance through their skills, work experience and good working relationship with stakeholders.
	Outcome of Understanding Compensation and Benefits	Knowing the benefits offered by the company will help employees be motivated by explaining compensation and benefits upon appraisal.
5 & 6	Drivers of Total Leadership	Managers evaluate the needs of employees and provide benefits in accordance with the law through orientation and open communication at all levels.
	Effect of leader's communication	Communication of vision is the starting point of acting on achieving the company's targets by clear directions of leaders and cooperation among the employees.
	Leader's communication Venues	Employees need to know the status or issues of the company that may affect them by having general assemblies and information sharing.
7 & 8	Professional advancement	I am interested to further widen my set skills by learning new things.
	Contribution of fair pay to profit	The compensation and benefits of the employee make him satisfied and contribute to high profits. The employee works efficiently and effectively to maximize the resources of the company.
	Reasons for career advancement	I feel that my performance will improve if my career grows in the company, and this will contribute to the average profit by achieving my KPIs that would certainly contribute to profit goals.
	Knowledge of compensation and benefits	If an employee will understand his benefits, then he will not feel that he receives less package than other employees by explaining their compensation and benefits before they even start working.
9 & 10	Outcomes of Motivation	Employee motivation results in proactiveness that maximizes company resources. However, the demand for product is down during the pandemic due to low financial capability.
	Result of proper Communication	Overall communication was vital in contributing to the sales growth of the company. However, I can say that during pandemic, there is a big decrease in sales across all industries.
	Contributing factors of inter-department communication	If there is smooth communication between inter-departments, goals are achieved at a much smoother and faster rate. This is done by creating team building programs that involve various departments.
	Leadership factors contributing to sales growth	Employees execute the plans of the top management. Recognition and incentives are given to loyalty awardees.
11 & 12	Compensation and benefits factors for achieving sales growth	Compensation is a factor of employee's engagement in work by having competitive compensation and benefits offered by management. Employees are paid more for their work during the pandemic. Even during the ECQ, the employees continued to receive their salaries and were allowed to use their leaves in advance even if they had not yet earned. There is a decrease in the sales growth because of the pandemic.
	Basis for leadership	Hiring of qualified leader by micromanaging to minimize resources and maximize output.
	Contributions of Nature of Job	Job improvements help lower operating costs through Kaizen competition. New government regulations during pandemic increased operating cost of the company.
	Effect of proper job knowledge	Understanding of job reduces operating cost by minimizing errors.
	Outcomes for job security	Company is still thriving even in pandemic through employees' cooperation towards company goals.
	Contributors of profit	Employee's awareness that profit affects compensation and benefits by being cost conscious and participating in Kaizen activities.
13 & 14	Effect of leader's communication	The company's vision helps employees understand their work clearly by its dissemination inside and outside the company.
	Contribution of Leaders	Leaders are proven to lead employees by meeting customer needs and adapting new technology for better quality of services and products.
	Consideration of employees	Employees are the executor of programs for customer's total support by prioritizing their concerns.
	Leader's communication venues	Sharing information with employees for their awareness by suggesting ideas that may help resolve issues in the company.
15 & 16	Outcome of developing skills	Opportunity to be multi-tasking by studying other areas for additional learnings.
	Contribution of Leadership	Clear communication of leader's commitment to quality through established quality control and regular conduct of internal/external controls/audits.
	Effect of leader's communication	The company's vision reflects on product quality by understanding what the client needs along with the vision for better output.
	Leadership's regard for taking feedback	Having regular meetings to discuss current company issues and listen to employee concerns.
	Factors affecting internal process	Well-compensated employees are motivated to perform beyond expectations for the company by maximizing resources. The implementation of new government or company policies might affect or limit the productivity of employee.
	Factors for achieving internal process improvement	Being paid fairly can be a factor in a company's service quality through the motivation it brings in doing jobs. But if employee is complacent with his work performance, product/service quality will not improve.
	Reasons for improving internal process	By sharing ideas, employees see different aspects to perform their jobs through Kaizen activities.
17 & 18	Reasons for improving internal process	Employee's growth with the company enables concern on the image and quality of the company by doing well in jobs.
	Leadership Actions	Improvements in the process will enhance products and services offered which will also make transactions easier and attract new clients.
	Leadership communication goals	Leader's clear dissemination of goals to all employees through regular meetings and discussion of company issues.
	Purpose of Leader's communication	Employees are well-informed about issues and can anticipate the possible problems arising from the issues and be able to propose countermeasures through discussion in meetings.
	Factors affecting learning innovations	Being innovative can lead employees to develop new skills which is beneficial for new career opportunities in the company.
	Contribution of career growth	Company ensures professional growth by widening skills of employees and offering challenging tasks as opportunities for new learnings and advancement.

IV. Strategies for Implementation of Company M to Increase Employee Engagement Towards Organizational Performance

The results of the quantitative analysis of this research shown in Figure 2 were used by the researcher in formulating the following strategies: 1) reinforcement of the leadership team by enhancing leadership skills and commitment, designing meaningful work, and providing resources and coaching employees, and having formal succession planning program; 2) development of career opportunities by creating a career path program, regular update of job descriptions, clarification of performance standards and integration of training and development; 3) improvement of compensation and benefits by making it competitive and having a formal salary structure, 4) intensification of communication through the formation of internal communications team and gaining employee's trust through transparency, 5) enhancement of nature of job by finalizing job evaluation program and giving employees variety of tasks where their skills can be stimulated, 6) focusing strategies for Models 5 and 6 with the highest adjusted R-squared and 7) creation of an organizational performance risk response team from the management team whose task is to formulate action plans to help lessen the impact of Covid-19 in Company M.

Conclusions

The following conclusions were arrived at: 1) The level of organizational performance of Company M would serve as basis to further enhance its engagement strategies towards maximizing its overall organizational performance especially on its financial dimensions and achieve "Very Good Relative Performance" level; 2) The resulting level of employee engagement suggested that Company M must make both tangible and intangible efforts to achieve a highly engaged workforce by putting more emphasis on its compensation and benefits indicators; 3) The resulting 18 models showed that leadership was the strongest significant predictor and that almost all the significant engagement predictors had positive effect while six models had negative effect to the organizational variables; and 4) Company M should emphasize the reinforcement of its leadership team as this factor proved to be the strongest predictor of organizational performance and focus on reversing the negative effect of significant employee engagement predictors. It is also equally important to consider enhancing the other significant employee engagement factors as these contributed significantly to organizational performance.

Recommendations

Based on the summary of significant findings and conclusions presented, the researcher derived the following recommendations:

1. That Company M adopt the strategies formulated in this research for the purpose of increasing employee engagement towards organizational performance.

2. That a similar research study be conducted by other researchers covering all employees to have holistic scope on the perceptions of the employees across the company.
3. That a related study be conducted by other researchers involving any other company or companies in similar industries with the same objective of improving employee engagement towards organizational performance. It would provide more rational and sound data that can be beneficial for the company or companies.
4. That a study be conducted by other researchers to further cover other employee engagement and organizational performance indicators. Through this, more comprehensive information on how to make more effective strategies will be arrived at on the grounds of more extensive and reliable findings.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

As this study involved human participants, the ethical concerns were considered during the design of research and were approved by the Letran Graduate School and Company M management before the data collection began. The ethical concerns of informed consent, risk of harm, confidentiality and anonymity and conflict of interests were considered. The researcher secured the necessary approvals from the Letran Graduate School before the research commenced. The name of the company was codified as Company M and there was no need to collect the names of the employees. A Letter of Intent was submitted to the Human Resources Management and Development Department of Company M to allow the employees to become the subjects of the study. Then, the informed consent of employees was secured before participation in the study. Any personal or other information gathered was treated with strict confidentiality in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012. The data collection and processing and interpretation of results were done by the researcher. Bias in the results and conflict of interest were avoided and, at the same time, the participant was protected from potential harm and the validity and integrity of results were assured.

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